

THE ROLE OF PLANT TISSUE CULTURE AND BIOTECHNOLOGY IN THE PRODUCTION OF VIRUS-FREE POTATO PLANTING MATERIAL

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Plant tissue culture and biotechnology play a strategic role in modern agriculture by accelerating breeding programs, improving plant quality, and ensuring the production of disease-free and genetically uniform planting material. Potato (*Solanum tuberosum* L.), one of the world's most important food crops, is predominantly propagated vegetatively, which facilitates the accumulation and transmission of viral pathogens, leading to significant yield losses and reduced tuber quality. The potato tuber is an underground stem that enables the plant to reproduce vegetatively. As a result of long-term domestication, it has become a high-yielding, carbohydrate-rich food crop [2].

In Azerbaijan, potato production is higher in the western regions of the country, particularly in districts such as Gadabay, Tovuz, and Shamkir [6]. According to FAOSTAT (2025), potato imports in Azerbaijan exceeded exports in 2024 (149,206 tons and 48,345 tons, respectively) [4]. Therefore, the implementation of new and innovative methods in potato cultivation is essential to increase production.

This study aimed to evaluate the effectiveness of shoot apical meristem culture combined with micropropagation techniques for the production of virus-free planting material in early-maturing potato cultivars [7,11]. Four local cultivars Telman, Ugur, Vagif, and Cenlibel were used as plant material. Prior to meristem excision, sprouted tubers were subjected to thermotherapy at 37 ± 1 °C for 28 days to reduce viral load. Isolated meristems were cultured on Murashige and Skoog (MS) [9] medium supplemented with different concentrations of plant growth regulators, including 6-benzylaminopurine (BAP), gibberellic acid (GA₃), kinetin (Kin), and indole-3-butyric acid (IBA).

Micropropagation was conducted through four stages: initiation, shoot multiplication, rooting and acclimatization. In vitro regenerated plantlets were screened for Potato virus Y (PVY), Potato leafroll virus (PLRV) and Potato virus X (PVX) using the DAS-ELISA method. The results revealed that meristem culture was highly effective in virus elimination, with an overall virus-free rate of 92.1%. The Ugur cultivar exhibited the highest virus elimination efficiency (100%), while Telman showed the lowest (80%). The regenerated plants did not exhibit any signs of PVX infection.

The composition of the culture medium and genotype significantly influenced morphogenetic responses, including shoot initiation, multiplication rate and rooting efficiency. Among the studied cultivars, Ugur demonstrated superior in vitro performance, indicating its suitability for large-scale propagation.

In conclusion, the integration of plant tissue culture and biotechnological approaches into potato breeding and seed production systems enables the rapid multiplication of virus-free, genetically stable planting material, reduces breeding cycle duration and supports sustainable potato production under local agro-climatic conditions.

Table 1. Number and virus-free status of seedlings developed in vitro from meristems isolated from infected potato tubers.

Order №	Variety name	Isolated meristem Number	In vitro development from meristem			Virus clearance rate (%)
			Total seedling number	Number of seedlings infected with the virus	Number of healthy seedlings	
1	Ugur	25	27	-	27	100.00
2	Cenlibel	32	29	1 (PLRV)	28	96.55
3	Vagif	30	25	3 (PLRV)	22	88.00
4	Telman	28	20	4 (PVY)	16	80.00

	Total	115	101	8	93	92.10
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